

9

Toward Global Dissemination of Indigenous Knowledge: the case of Raffia Artisans in Ikot Ekpene Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria

By

Ntui, A.I and Ottong, E.J
ntuinju@yahoo.com & enojoseph2001@yahoo.com

Abstract

The main thrust of the paper is the role of the librarians, library and ICT in global dissemination of indigenous knowledge. The empirical case study is the art and craft of raffia work in Ikot Ekpene, with a view to increase and improve the available information of the unique indigenous knowledge. The people of Ikot Ekpene have developed exceptional skills in transforming raffia fibers into shoes, assorted handbags including conference bags (and packages) belts, hats, mats, decorative apparels, bangles and numerous articles of fashion. Presently, the market for the raffia product is limited to local demand and is of attraction to only a few tourists. There is however great need to disseminate information on the product of this peculiar indigenous knowledge globally. This paper suggest that libraries should act as a clearing house for collecting, documenting, preserving and disseminating information on raffia craft knowledge systems. Librarians should publicize raffia craft activities and services through modern ICT, exhibition, workshops, conferences and seminars. The nation should be brought into the areas of security, protecting the rights of the indigenous artisans in terms of their cultural and intellectual property.

Introduction

Indigenous Knowledge (IK) refers to the unique, traditional local knowledge existing within and developed around the specific conditions of a community, indigenous to a particular geographical area on which their livelihoods and survival depend (Steiner, 2007). It develops over centuries, therefore represents all the skills and innovations of a people, and embodies the collective wisdom and resourcefulness of a community. Indigenous knowledge is unique to a specific culture and plays an important role in defining the identity of a community. Like many tropical societies, the Ikot Ekpene people have developed a unique indigenous knowledge of use of *raffia palm*.

Ikot Ekpene local government area, known throughout Nigeria as "The Raffia City", is a town, in the South-South zone of Nigeria, in the densely populated state of Akwa Ibom. The town is situated by the coastal highway between Calabar and Aba. Ikot Ekpene has a long history of transforming the raffia fiber into shoes, hats, handbags, mats and other articles of fashion. For centuries, Ikot Ekpene people have produced handmade raffia items to meet the practical needs of everyday life. Such handicrafts are also expressions of their makers' skills and of personal styles. The raffia craft (indigenous to the area) has gained centre stage and a means of gaining economic stability and wealth for many indigenes of the area, thus the town enjoys the pseudonym as the *raffia city*

Today, the raffia craft is at risk of becoming extinct because of rapidly changing and fast pacing cultural changes in Ikot Ekpene. Oral paths (which are the major means of dissemination) are being blocked as people no longer stay in homogenous community blocks. In addition, children are being sent to formal schools with little or no time left for learning the craft. The youngsters are becoming disinterested in their native culture because outside influence provides them with a negative view of their culture and traditional practices. Thus, there is a risk that within one generation, the knowledge could be lost for ever as the knowledge systems of these raffia artisans have never been recorded systematically in any form; hence they are not easily accessible to researchers, and development practitioners. However, these researchers believed that raffia craft has much to offer and teach the world at large, and only by research, documentation and dissemination can it be preserved and made available to development workers world wide and its uses exploited. There was, therefore, a strong

need for a research devoted solely to the documentation, and dissemination of indigenous knowledge of raffia craft in Ikot Ekpene. This study therefore was conducted to fill this knowledge gap by increasing awareness, improving the available information; documentation and dissemination of information on indigenous knowledge of raffia artisans in Ikot Ekpene area.

Research Methods

The data for this work were gathered through oral traditions, questionnaire, interviews and observation. Similar methods were used in other indigenous knowledge programmes in Ghana , (Emeagwali, 2003) Ecuador, (Sustainable Development Update, 2005), Tanzania , (Ole-Lengisugi, 1996), Nigeria , (Philips & Titilola, 1995) and was in conformity with the World Bank Guidelines (1999) for description and measurement of indigenous knowledge. The researchers explained to the crafts persons, in detail, the study objectives and the possible benefits of the study. Also the crafts persons were informed that the researchers have come to learn from them and will not take much of their time. The researchers are indigenes of Ikot Ekpene, and so could speak the local language and are more at home with ideas, views of life and practices in this area. They can give first hand account about the themes in strict accordance. This made the fieldwork much easier as they could understand the meaning of local terms, the local conditions, including indigenous knowledge systems and practices. The most interesting aspect of the information gathering exercise was the oral tradition, where collective testimonies and recollections of the past inherited from earlier generations were transmitted in various forms of verbal testimonies to the researchers. The researchers had extensive interviewing with the local experts in raffia craft. At a preliminary stage, the researchers were fully sensitive to the status of the provider of information, his or her stake in the system and the various versions of the traditional explanation given. There was a clear understanding of whether or not the orally transmitted information is myth, legend, proverb, chant, praise song or of unidentified or unidentifiable origin. These narrations were recorded in audio taped. Initially there was reluctance by crafts persons to share information, as they felt that dissemination of raffia craft practices could lead to the dis-empowerment of indigenous people. However, during the interviewing process, the researchers assured them that techniques of their skills will not be published, so friendly conversation and inter personal relationship developed between the researchers and respondents.

Discussion of Findings

Cultural Belief System

Raffia artisans have adapted cultural belief systems that demonstrate an immense knowledge and respect for the Earth. These systems contain rules that define how the environment should be treated. Enforcement of these customs and norms is often ensured by social conformity and by codified threats. It is a system of taboos concerned with spirits that are believed to control the raffia craft. By ritual and magic, the 'Abasi ayop' are able to influence these supernatural forces to benefit them. All artisans have access to supernatural powers, but some are considered to be especially endowed. With proper training these people are known as practicing 'Ada osung' and are able to contact supernatural forces and help in establishing spiritual harmony among the group. This finding is similar to Melville (2005), and Cintron, & Yara, (2005) who observed that most tropical indigenous knowledge have system of beliefs where various supernatural forces are involved.

Resource Use

The raffia artisans rely on the raffia palm for survival. Rituals, ceremonies and prohibitions all regulate the use of raffia palm and accomplish the goals of resource management and a balanced ecosystem. . For example, raffia fibers cannot be removed from same palm tree more than once a month. Enforcement of these customs and norms is often ensured by social conformity and by codified threats. Once raffia palm tree is felled, the tree is brought from the swamp, cut up and is divided among relatives and friends of the crew. Excess raffia is stored in 'ubium' for use during the raining seasons when swamps are impenetrable and the resources are scarce. This finding is consistent with investigations of Clay, (1996) and Larson, (1998), that indigenous groups all over the world have adapted systems that contain rules that define how the environment should be treated. .

How raffia craft knowledge is stored, exchanged and disseminated

Raffia craft knowledge is stored in peoples' memories and activities and is expressed in the form of stories, songs, folklore, proverbs, dances, myths, cultural values, beliefs, rituals, community laws. Raffia craft is

predominantly embedded in practices and experiences. Raffia craft knowledge is most commonly exchanged through personal communication and demonstration. It is transmitted orally, or through imitation and demonstration from master to apprentice, from parents to children. A unique system which employed symbolic representation (*eyei*) is used in communicating among members of exclusive craft. *Eyeyi*, which refers to the fresh unopened leaves of the palm frond, can be tied or shaped in different forms to convey different messages. Although raffia craft is readily shared among members of the same house hold, it is generally shared to a lesser degree across the community. It is learnt through repetition, which aids in the retention and reinforcement of raffia craft. There are also restrictions on accessibility of raffia craft within the community. Beyond a few trained individuals or families that pass the skills from master to apprentice, or from parent to child, it is considered restricted information. Some aspects of raffia craft knowledge is tacit therefore, not easily codifiable. This is because, in most cases, the exchange of craft knowledge is ingrained in cultural values, which cannot easily be recognized by an external observer. For instance, various messages can be communicated through drumming, understood only by craft persons. For instance, faced with an impending disaster like a craft person being drown in the swamps, the *Ada usung I* (leader) beats specific drums and sound horns to craft persons to assemble at known meeting points where specific advice or instructions are communicated and appropriate preparedness and response actions are decided upon. Similar findings were obtained by Purcell, (1998) that IK is shared and communicated orally, by specific examples and through culture. The raffia artisans have well-developed structures through which the craft information is disseminated. The structures include a leader which has at its disposal, the speed and strength of numerous young people that could be used to investigate a particular phenomenon or to pass on urgent messages upon need.

Raffia artisans do not freely share their expertise and belief with others, as it is a means of livelihood, and has potential commercial value. The fact that they alone are the holders of it puts them in a favorable position. Also, it could lead to exploitation should the information be secured by certain parties who could patent the methodologies, and then not only use the knowledge for commercial reasons. This finding is similar to Waters-Bayar (1994) relating to the production of a fermented milk drink called *nono* by women in Nigeria . To guard against urban businessmen capitalizing on the women's innovations, expertise was not freely shared. Similarly, the

World Bank showed some level of caution in releasing the document by Ole-Lengisugi (1996) on Ethno botanical Practices amongst the Maasai,

The Way Forward

The way forward in global dissemination of raffia craft knowledge lies with the librarians, libraries, information centers and ICT. No longer is the library primarily a depository of books nor the librarian mainly a caretaker and custodian. Library could help in awareness creation, and successful integration of raffia craft into the development process. Initially, the initiative would focus on awareness building among decision-makers in development organizations and the national governments. Librarians could promote approaches to increase rural people's awareness of wealth they possess and help them to further enrich it.

Developing database of success stories, best practices, lessons from the raffia craft and provide access to these databases. Reports of raffia craft practices could be collected and summarized in a publicly accessible database that also connects to the original source of information wherever possible. Cases could be published in a monthly periodical. The initiative would on a pilot basis help to enhance the capacity of existing raffia crafts to improve their networking among peers as well as to capture and disseminate raffia craft information. International databases that responsibly make accessible all information that has been documented, could effectively serve to educate and guide policy makers towards more appropriate and sustainable development solutions.

Another way forward lies with Information and communication technology. As countries establish connectivity, modern ICT could become a powerful enabler for the exchange of raffia craft,. External support to help build local capacity for dissemination could focus on videos and radio broadcasts in local languages, telecenters and electronic networking, especially among local indigenous knowledge centers. Although digitization is ideal for sharing, exchanging, educating and preserving indigenous cultures, it also creates ample opportunities for illicit access to and misuse of traditional knowledge. It is essential that librarians apply IT security mechanisms be able to define and control the rights and access to their resources, in order to uphold traditional laws; prevent the misuse of raffia indigenous heritage. Dissemination of raffia craft practices could lead to the dis-empowerment of indigenous people. To protect the intellectual

property rights of raffia artisans librarians could, without compromising the principle of global knowledge partnership ensure that royalties are paid before users are allowed access to databases.

Conclusion

The paper sees raffia craft in Ikot Ekpene, Akwa Ibom State as an underutilized resource in the development process. This is so because inadequate attention was given to research and documentation of this unique indigenous knowledge. It is the position of this paper that libraries, information centers, librarians and related professionals in ICT have important roles to play in the dissemination of indigenous knowledge. It calls for more studies on the success stories of raffia craft in Ikot Ekpene in order to understand the content, context and socio economic relevance of the craft.

References

- Cintron, Gilberto & Yara Schaeffer (2005) The Mega Tsunami of 26 December 2004: Recognizing Ecological Lesson from a Large-Scale Natural Disaster. <http://www.iucn.org/tsunami/docs/ecological-lessons-large-scale-disturbances.pdf>
- Clay, J.W. (1996) Generating Income and Conserving Resources: Twenty Lessons from the Field. *Sustainable Development Update*, World Wildlife Fund, Washington D.C. .
- Emeagwali ,G (2003) African Indigenous Knowledge Systems: Implications for the Curriculum,"_IN Toyin Falola (ed), *Ghana in Africa and the World: Essays in Honor of Adu Boahen*, African World Press. New Jersey .
- Grenier, L. (1998) *Working with Indigenous Knowledge - A Guide for Researchers*, IDRC, Ottawa
- Kothari, B. 1995. "From Aural to written: the documentation of Knowledge in Ecuador ." *Indigenous Knowledge and Development Monitor*_ Vol. 3, Issue 2. pp 9-13
- Larson, J. (1998) Perspectives on indigenous knowledge systems in Southern Africa. Washington D.C. *World Bank Discussion paper No.3*

- Melville, Manmohan, (2005) 'Tsunami Warning System of Aboriginal Tribes', <http://www.gatewayforindia.com/articles/tsunami.htm>
- Ole-Lengisugi, N. A. M. 1996. The Role of Indigenous Knowledge in Sustainable Ecology and Ethnobotanical Practices among Pastoral Maasai Olkenerei-Le-Simanjiro Experience. Tanzania, Maasai Resource Centre For Indigenous Knowledge (MARECIK).
- Philips, A. O. & Titilola, T. 1995. *Indigenous Knowledge Systems and Practices. Case Studies from Nigeria.* Ibadan, Nigeria. Nigerian Institute of Social and Economic Research (NISER).
- Purcell, T. W., 1998. "Indigenous Knowledge and Applied Anthropology: Questions of Definition and Direction." *Human Organization*. Vol. 57, No 3 Fall.
- Steiner, A, (2007) Indigenous Knowledge In disaster management Issue 6 April 2007 *Environmental Emergencies News* UNEP Publication
- Sustainable Development Update, Issue 1, Volume 5, 2005 <http://www.albaeco.com/sdu/20/index.htm>
- Waters-Bayar, A. 1994. "The ethics of documenting rural people's knowledge: investigating milk marketing among Fulani Women in Nigeria". Scoones, I. Thompson, J. and Chambers, R. (eds.) pp 144-147. *Beyond Farmer First. Rural people's knowledge, agricultural research and extension practice.* London. Intermediate Technology Publications.
- World Bank. (2008). The Indigenous Knowledge Initiative. Internet Source: <http://www.worldbank.org/html/afr/ik/newdatab.htm>
- World Bank Development Report (1999): 'Knowledge for Development, Oxford University Press, London.